

ID	Graphical representation	Related paper	Node or Link
GRAY DOTTED ARROW		1	LINK
BLACK DOTTED ARROW		1	LINK
BLACK ARROW		1	LINK
OBJECTIVE WITH THICK EDGES		1	Node
AGENT WITH DOLL		1	Node
DOTTED RECTANGLE		1	Node
parallelogram		1	Node
link with white ball		1	LINK

DOTTED ARROW

1

LINK

BOLD ARROW

1

LINK

and-refinement

2

Node

or-refinement

2

Node

REQUIREMENT 1

2

Node

REQUIREMENT 2

2

Node

REQUIREMENT 3

2

Node

REQUIREMENT 4

2

Node

REQUIREMENT 5

2

Node

Demand

3

LINK

Contribute

3

LINK

Guarantee

3

LINK

During

3

LINK

Before

3

LINK

After

3

LINK

Condition

3

LINK

ARROW WITH X

3

LINK

BOLD OBSTACLE

4

Node

BOLD ARROW

4

LINK

TRAPEZUS

4

Node

ROW (AGENT CONNECTOR TO REQUIREMENT)

4

LINK

Achieve goal

4

Node

Maintain goal

4

Node

Safety

5

NODE

Security		5	NODE
REFINEMENT		6	Node
dotted parallelogram		6	Node
link with a pair of values		6	Node
arrow with a pair of values		6	LINK
refinement		7	NODE
Agent		7	NODE
Refines		7	LINK

Variant		7	NODE
TIME AND SPACE		8	Node
Wheel		8	Node
SOFTWARE AGENT		9	Node
HUMAN AGENT		9	Node
UML CLASS		9	Node
OBJECTIVE		9	Node
LINK TO SECUREUML		9	LINK

IE WITH BLACK CIRCLE, LINK RESPONSIBILITY

9

LINK

CROSSLINE (LINK REFINEMENT)

9

LINK

CONFLICT

9

LINK

Permission

9

Node

CLOUD

10

Node

op

10

Node

RELATIONSHIP AND

10

LINK

DOTTED ARROW

10

LINK

rectangle with rounded vertices		10	Node
DOTTED LINE		10	LINK
Assumption		11	Node
Attack		11	Node
Threat		11	Node
Vulnerability		11	Node
Exploits		11	LINK
CONTRIBUTIONS TO		11	LINK

softgoal	Softgoal	11	Node
Deception Technique	Deception Technique	11	Node
Deception Tactic	Deception Tactic	11	Node
Conflict	Conflict	11	LINK
Security control	Security Control	11	Node
Mitigates	Mitigates	11	LINK
Requirement	Requirement	11	Node
Applies	Applies	11	Node

AGENT WITH DOLL

12

Node

Output

Output

12

LINK

Input

Input

12

LINK

Monitoring

13

LINK

Output

Output

13

LINK

striped arrow

13

LINK

complement square

13

Node

request

13

Node

GRAY ARROW		14	LINK
Arrow		14	LINK
transformation		14	Node
REPRESENTATION OF A FLAG		15	Node
CONDITION		15	Node
CIRCLE IN THE MIDDLE OF A RELATIONSHIP LINE		15	LINK
INFORMATION		15	Node
HUMAN AGENT		16	Node

Achieved softgoal		16	Node
Obstructs/denies		16	LINK
mitigates		16	LINK
Domain assumption		16	Node
FUNCTION		17	Node
DEPENDENCE		17	Node
ternary link		17	LINK
rectangle with rounded vertices		17	Node

Details		17	Node
ternary link with arrow		18	LINK
TRIPLE BOX		18	Node
Link like UML aggregation		18	LINK
AGENT		18	Node
Refines		18	Node
GRAY BOX		18	Node
ENTITY IN GRAY COLOR		18	Node

GOAL		G	19	Node
EXPECTATION		E	19	Node
ENVIRONMENT AGENT		EA	19	Node
OBSTACLE		O	19	Node
EVENT		Ev	19	Node
DOMAIN HYPOTHESIS		DH	19	Node
REQUIREMENTS		R	19	Node
SOFTGOAL		S	19	Node

SYSTEM AGENT		19	Node
OPERATION		19	Node
ENTITY		19	Node
DOMAIN INVARIANT		19	Node
Concerns		20	LINK
Performance		20	LINK
dotted parallelogram		21	Node
link with a wheel		21	LINK

Plus		21	Node
arrow with a textual description		22	LINK
link with a textual description		22	Node
ternary link with arrow		22	LINK
dotted parallelogram		22	Node
arrow in black		22	LINK
REFINEMENT		23	LINK
HUMAN AGENT		23	Node

SOFTGOAL		24	Node
Dotted arrow with filled head		24	LINK
and-refinement		24	LINK
or-refinement		24	LINK
Provide content		24	Node
COMPLETE AND		25	LINK
PARTIAL AND		25	LINK
COMPLETE OR		25	LINK

PARTIAL OR		25	LINK
OBSTRUCTION		25	LINK
AGENT		26	Node
ternary link with arrow		26	LINK
HARD GOAL		27	Node
SOFTGOAL		27	Node
NON-SYSTEM		27	Node
SEQUENTIAL	;	27	Node

PARALLEL		27	Node
EXCLUSIVE		27	Node
MANDATORY		27	LINK
OPTIONAL		27	LINK
ALTERNATIVE		27	LINK
OR		27	LINK
ternary link with arrow		28	LINK
Link like dependency		28	LINK

Link like UML aggregation		29	LINK
Decomposition		29	LINK
AGENT WITH DOLL		29	Node
GOAL ID		30	NO
OPERATIONS		30	LINK
link with a wheel		31	LINK
DOTTED ARROW with open head		31	LINK
link with x		31	LINK

fine dotted parallelogram

31

Node

Id to goal

32

NODE

Id to goal

32

NODE

Id to goal

32

NODE

link with black ball

33

LINK

ternary link with arrow

33

LINK

Arrow with white head

34

LINK

STRATEGY

34

Node

DECOMPOSITION CONTINUES

34

Node

UNDEVELOPED GOAL

34

Node

GOAL

34

Node

SAVED BY

34

LINK

ternary link with arrow with black ball

35

LINK

ternary link with double arrow and black ball

35

LINK

HUMAN AGENT

35

Node

AGENT WITH A TRIANGLE

35

Node

parallelogram grey

36

Node

PROPERTIES

36

Node

link with an arch

37

LINK

Quality

37

Node

Quality

38

Node

Group goals in red

38

Node

Group goals in blue

38

Node

Group goals in black		38	Node
PARTIALLY SATISFIED GOAL		39	Node
VULNERABILITY		39	Node
DECOMPOSITION		39	LINK
NEGATIVE CONTRIBUTION		39	LINK
FACTOR (COMPONENT)		39	LINK
DOMAIN ASSUMPTION		39	Node
ternary link with arrow (yellow ball)		40	LINK

Parallelogram with shadow

41

Node

ternary link with arrow

41

LINK

rectangle with dotted rounded vertices

42

Node

yellow paralelogram dotted

42

Node

CROSSLINE

42

LINK

yellow paralelogram fine dotted

42

Node

red paralelogram

42

Node

Cause

43

Node

INPUT

43

Node

OUTPUT

43

Node

DOMAIN HYPOTESIS

44

Node

CAUSE

45

Node

INPUT

45

LINK

OUTPUT

45

LINK

: Newly generated parent goal

NEWLY GENERATED PARENT GOAL

46

NODE

INPUT 47 LINK

OUTPUT 47 LINK

ATTACK 48 LINK

LINKING 48 LINK

EXPLOIT 48 LINK

GATE 48 LINK

RESOLVES 49 LINK

OBSTRUCTS 49 LINK

REQUERIMENT

50

NODE

FUNCTION

50

NODE

CHARACTERISTIC

50

NODE

CONFLICT

50

NODE

DISPUTED PART

50

NODE